

A Clinical Approach on Legum Baccalaureus (LL B) Curriculum and The Role of an Advocate in Law Teaching

Dr D Kannan¹

Introduction

In the evolution of the judicial system in India, the legal profession has contributed more in social change². The British government issued a charter, 1726 which provided the establishment of Courts namely Mayor's Court in Madras, Calcutta and Bombay. The Mayor's Court heard civil suits with in the town and its subordinate factories and its being the court of record. In 1753, the earlier charter was modified. But the system of Mayor's Court was inefficient. The charter of 1774 contributed a lot in the field of legal profession in India.³ In 1801, the Supreme Court was established in Madras. The Supreme Court had power to remove any Advocate or attorney on reasonable cause. The term 'Advocate' was extended only to English and Irish Barristers and members of the faculty of Advocates in Scotland.

The term 'Attorney' was meant only the British Attorneys or Solicitors. The Advocates and Attorneys were eligible for practice and not the Indian legal practitioners. The Legal Practitioners Act, 1840 had provided that the people of any nationality or religion would be eligible to act as pleaders. Attorneys and Barristers were allowed to enroll in any of Her Majesty's Court in India. The Legal Practitioners Act⁴ 1879 was enacted to consolidated and amend the law relating to the legal practitioners. In 1923, a committee so called the Indian Bar Committee was constituted.

¹ Assistant Professor of Law (SG), School of Excellence in Law, The Tamil Nadu Dr Ambedkar Law University Chennai – 113, mail id: chinnachi_kannan@yahoo.com

² The Role of the Judiciary is a vital organ in the democratic society as guarantors of liberty and rights that would be secured more adequately if such rights are enforceable before the Courts of law than by mere declaration cited in a document.

³ J.P.S. SIROHI (2001), Professional Ethics, Accountancy for Lawyers and Bench Bar Relation, V edition, Allahabad Law Agency, Faridabad, p 3

⁴ Under section 5 of the Legal Practitioners Act, 1879 provides that every person entered as an Attorney on the roll of any High Court would be entitled to practice in all the courts subordinate to such High Courts.

The committee did not suggest the establishment of All India Bar Council. But the committee suggested some recommendation which was upheld in 1926. Indian Bar Council Act, 1926⁵ was consolidated and amended the law relating to legal practitioners in the courts in India. After the independence of India, the efforts were made to improve the efficiency of legal profession. In 1951, the All India Bar Committee was constituted under the Chairmanship of Justice S. R. Dass. On the report of the committee, All India Bar Council and State Bar Councils have been established. Prior to the Advocates Act, 1961 there were different kinds of legal practitioners in India like Advocate, Solicitor, Pleader, Vakil and Mukhtar they were registered and enrolled under various legal practitioners Acts. Now there is only one Legal Practitioners Act for the Advocate in the whole of India that is the Advocates Act, 1961. The Act, 1961 enumerates the provision for the admission and enrollment of Advocates.

Advocate and Legal Profession

The term 'Advocate' means an advocate entered in any roll under the provisions of the Act. The profession of advocate is monopolistic in character but the Bar is not a private guild, it is a public institution committed to public justice and pro bono publico service⁶. The duty of an advocate is to assist the court in the administration of justice. The practice of law has a public utility flavour. The Advocate must strictly and scrupulously abide by the code of conduct behaving the noble profession and must not indulge in any activity which may tend to lower the image of the legal profession in society⁷. The Advocate is an officer of the court, a privileged member of the society and a gentleman⁸. An Advocate is required to be absolutely fair to the court. He should make accurate statements of facts and should not twist the facts. He should not misguide the court by suppressing the relevant facts.

⁵ The purpose of the Indian Bar Council Act, 1926 was to provide for the incorporation of Indian Bar Council.

⁶ Bar Council of Maharashtra V. M.V. Dabholkar; AIR 1987 SC 242 in this case justice V.R. Krishna Iyer made this statement.

⁷ Supra Note 2

⁸ Chapter II in part IV of the Bar Council of India Rules, 1975 'Standards of Professional Conduct and Etiquette'

If the Advocate suppresses the facts that earlier an identical petition has been dismissed by court, it would amount to professional misconduct. The practicing advocates need for training and acquiring skills in oral and written communication, reasoning and persuasion, mediation and counseling, drafting and conveyance ,etc., legal aid to the poor and public interest litigation. The lawyer must be acquainted with the latest amendments.

The Lawyers have to study and understand the legal dimensions of poverty, urban problems, industrialization, pollution of the environment, bonded labour, atrocities against vulnerable groups, child exploitation, gender justice, violation of human rights and other society related issues.

The Chamber work of an Advocate

The Advocate interviews the client, advises them generally on their legal position and writes letters and also prepares briefs for counsel in legal proceedings in which counsel are employed. He should be able to interview all types of client in order to ascertain what their problem is. He should have knowledge of human nature, practical wisdom, and the ability to dictate a good letter. Naturally he needs a working knowledge of the law of procedure. A Lawyer should be well versed with the skills and concepts involved in obtaining an accurate and complete understanding of the case of the client. The information available from the client and others includes economic, technological and other factors relating to the problem such as nature of the client's financial position. The lawyer should be familiar with the skills and concepts involved in developing a plan of action with the client. Moreover, the client is in position to spend the financial expenditure in which the client is able and willing to devote.

The Lawyer sometimes has to assess yet another plan of action is that the matter is to be referred in whole or in part to another lawyer because it requires a degree of experience, knowledge or skill greater than the lawyer personally possesses. After such assessment, counseling the client is useful about the judgement of the lawyer.

A lawyer should be ensure that the case which is to be sued have not been ruled, limited or called into question. The lawyer should be familiar with the skills and processes required for dealing with documents effectively. The Lawyer should identify the documents that are pertinent to client's legal problems or its possible resolutions. He should analyse the documents, including identifying significant passages or portions of the documents and assessing the implications of the facts contained in these passages or portions for the present factual and legal theories.

The communication skill is a basic need for the legal profession. A lawyer has to employ communication skills including both written and oral in a wide variety of ways and range. The Advocate has to prove his communication skills while he drafts the petition, notice, representation etc., for submitting the same before the appropriate forum. The facts should be presented in an abstract and concrete fashion; articulating relevant legal issues; put forth the most powerful arguments through communication skills is only way to succeed the case.

The Lawyer is used to draft a substantial technical document, requirements for specialized kinds of writing including the drafting of executory documents such as contracts, wills, convents, corporate charters etc., in other kind is drafting of litigation documents that is pleadings, motions, affidavits, briefs and other memorandum of law. The process of counseling is an important part of the advocacy. The lawyers have to counsel to their clients about the decision or the course of action what they are considering. In order to counsel the client effectively a lawyer should at least be familiar with legal concepts and procedures involved in establishing a proper counseling relationship with a client, gathering information relevant to the decision to be made by the client, analyzing the decision to be made.

An Advocate should have an efficient working knowledge of functions and general organization of the courts, its basic concepts and jurisdiction. He should know the availability of alternative judicial forums and importance of choice of forums.

Presentation of the case

The presentation of a case before the court is an important duty of an Advocate. Before presentation of a case the lawyer should adduce the natural justice principle is that the issuance of legal notice to the other side. The notice is an announcement or intimation about his presentation of the case. The notice may be given by the party himself or by his agent or by his pleader. In some cases notices are mandatory⁹ and in some cases it is an obligatory.

There is no prescribed form in the issuance of notice. It may be given on the basis of the facts and circumstances of the case. Where a counsel by mistake sent notice without signature or his office copy such notice won't be a defective notice¹⁰. It is only a mistake.

The notice must contain the following particulars

1. Date of notice
2. The name and address of the person who gives the notice
3. The name and address of the person who is entitled to receive the notice
4. Brief facts of claim
5. Cause of action for the notice
6. Relief claimed

The notice is the foundation of the case hence before preparing the notice the counsel should see the latest provision of law regarding the fact in issue. The mode of service of notice is most important. It may be delivered through registered post with acknowledgement due. Notice under section 80 Civil Procedure Code notice is that a two

⁹AIR 1969 SC 1256; failure to serve notice complying with the requirements of the statute will entail the dismissal of the suit.

¹⁰AIR 1962 Pat. 303

months' notice should be issued in a suit against either state government or central government or a public officer.

Once a notice is issued the other party has to issue reply notice. The opposite party in his notice may state that the counsel is to advise the client after aware of the facts.

CONSTITUTION OF CIVIL COURTS

DISTRICT MUNSIF

|

SUB – COURT

|

DISTRICT COURT

|

HIGH COURT

|

SUPREME COURT

FILING PROCESS OF CIVIL SUITS

Every suit or proceeding shall be instituted by the presentation of a plaint¹¹ or a petition.

The presentation of plaint must be on a working day and during office hours. The following are the stages of the civil suits

Filing of a Plaint by Plaintiff

the particulars of the suit will be entered by the court in a book kept for the said purpose, which is called register of the civil suits¹²

|

-Numbering-

After presentation the plaint will be scrutinized by the Stamp Reporter, if there are defects, the counsel will remove the same, thereafter the suit will be numbered the suit

|

¹¹The expression 'plaint' has not been defined in CPC but it means " a private memorial tendered to a court in which the person sets forth his cause of action; the exhibition of an action in writing (Assan V. Pathumma (1899) 22 Mad 494)

¹²Order VII Rule 2 of CPC, 1908

Appearance of the party¹³ the party the suit to attend the court in person or by their pleader on the day fixed.

|

Service of Summons to Defendant¹⁴

the service of summons to the defendant is a condition precedent to a fair trial

|

Appearance of the Defendant¹⁵

He has to file a vakalat and enter the appearance

|

Filing of Written Statement¹⁶ by Defendant

A defendant should present a written statement of his defence within 30 days from the service of the summons on him

|

First hearing of the suit¹⁷

The day on which the issues are framed is the first hearing starts as well in a small cause suit the first hearing would be the day on which the trial starts¹⁸

|

Framing of Issues¹⁹

|

Filing of Documents

|

Trial of the Suit

|

¹³Order IX Rule 1 – 12 of CPC; no proceeding in a court of law should be conducted to the detriment of any party in his absence.

¹⁴ Order V Rule 1 CPC– the court shall issue the summons to the defendant calling upon to appear and therein answer the claim of the plaintiff within 30 days from the institution of the suit and file a written statement.

¹⁵ Order V Rule 3 CPC - to attend the court in person or by their pleader

¹⁶ Order VIII Rule 1 CPC- the expression written statement is the pleading of the defendant wherein he deals with every material fact alleged by the plaintiff in his plaint and also states new facts in his favour or takes legal objections against the claim of the plaintiff.

¹⁷The first hearing means the day on which the court goes into the pleadings of the parties in order to understand their contentions.

¹⁸ Sangram singh V. Election Tribunal , AIR 1955 SC 425

¹⁹ Order XIV Rule 1 of CPC

Every Suit shall be instituted in the court of the lowest grade in which competent to try it. If a suit is filed before the court of justice the following are the stages of the civil court proceedings

Supreme Court
(Special Leave Petition)

Where Interlocutory Application (I A) is ordered in accordance with the merits of the case and such I A is an appealable one, the following are the procedure in the case of IA

Interlocutory Application
(Appealable Order)

Before the trial court, where the trial court is DMC then the CMA before District Court

|

Civil Miscellaneous Application

(Where in the IA is disposed off by the District Court the CMA will be before the High Court)

|

Civil Revision Petition

|

Special Leave Petition

Where Interlocutory Application is ordered in accordance with the merits of the case and such I A is non- appealable one, the following are the procedure

Interlocutory Application
(Non-appealable Order)

|

Civil Revision Petition (C R P)
(Under Art. 227 of constitution of India)

|

Special Leave Petition

The institution of the civil suit has begun only by filing a plaint filed under Order VII Rule 1 of Civil Procedure Code. A plaint is a statement of plaintiff's claim. It is a relief sought for by the plaintiff against the defendant. The following are the contents of a plaint.

1. Cause title

IN THE COURT OF THE DISTRICT MUNSIF _____

O.S. No. _____ of 2024

ABC

Plaintiff

-VS-

XYZ

Defendant

Plaint filed under Order VII Rule 1 of CPC

- The address for service of the Plaintiff
- The address for service of the Defendant
- The Facts of the Case is to be narrated
- The cause of action and jurisdiction to be mentioned
- The valuation of the suit
- The prayer sought for
- Counsel for plaintiff Plaintiff (signature)
- Verification
- Dated at _____ this _____ day of _____ 2024
- Plaintiff (signature)
- Schedule of Property
- Verification
- Dated at _____ this _____ day of _____ 2024
- Plaintiff (signature)
- List of Documents filed under Order VII Rule 14 (1) of CPC
- Dated at _____ this _____ day of _____ 2024
- Plaintiff (signature)

- List of Documents filed under Order VII Rule 14 (2) of CPC
 - Dated at _____ this _____ day of _____ 2024
 - Plaintiff (signature)
 - Statement regarding registered addresses of the parties under Order VI Rule 14A of CPC
-

While presenting the plaint the following documents are to be filed before the court

1. Original Plaint
2. Vakalat
3. Process Application
4. Suit Summons
5. True copy of the plaint
6. Documents under Order VII Rule 14(1) of CPC

If an injunction has to be filed the following are necessary

1. Urgent or Emergent Petition
2. Interlocutory Application along with Affidavit
3. True copy of Interlocutory Application along with Affidavit
4. Suit Notice

After the civil court issued a summons complied the provisions of CPC (Order V) The defendant has to file his defences through the Written Statement under Order VIII of CPC. The defendant should see the plaint and its documents then he can even raise the preliminary objections. The court can hear the case on the basis of preliminary objections at the first hearing as the procedure laid down under CPC. The following are the preliminary objections

1. jurisdictional issues; a) territorial; b) pecuniary
2. valuation of the suit
3. suit bar by the limitation or the provisions of civil nature

The defendant has a right to file an additional written statement in which the plaint has been amended. When the plaintiff has failed to present the written statement in time then the court shall pronounce judgement, as thinks fit.

Constitution of criminal courts

JUDICIAL MAGISTRATE I CLASS

|

CHIEF JUDICIAL MAGISTRATE

|

DISTRICT CUM SESSIONS

|

HIGH COURT

|

SUPREME COURT

Presentation of case in criminal courts

All offences under any other law shall be investigated, inquired into, tried, and otherwise dealt with according to the same provisions, but subject to any enactment for the time being in force regulating the manner or place of investigating, inquiring into, trying or otherwise dealing with such offences²⁰ the jurisdiction is given under this provision would be excluded only when a special Act applies and the jurisdiction of the regular courts to try particular cases under IPC²¹. A crime is a wrong not only against the individual victim but also against the society at large. It is because of this consideration that the State, representing the people in their collective capacity, participates in criminal trial as party against the person accused of crime more particularly if the crime is a cognizable offence. The Public Prosecutor or the Assistant Public Prosecutor is the counsel for the state in such trials.

The object of a criminal trial is to find out the truth and to determine the guilt or innocence of the accused. The duty of the prosecutor in such a trial is not merely to secure conviction

²⁰ Under section 4 of Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973

²¹ Bhim Sen V. State of U.P. AIR 1955SC 435

at all costs but to place before the court whatever evidence is possessed by the prosecutor, whether it be in favour of or against the accused, and to leave the court to decide upon all such evidence²². The cognizance of offence by a magistrate implies that the magistrate has applied his mind to the offence alleged in the complaint or police report with a view to take further proceedings necessary for the trial of the accused person. The magistrate may issue the summons or warrant for the purpose of securing the attendance of the accused at the time of trial.

Private Complaint

A magistrate may take cognizance of an offence on a complaint, shall examine upon oath the complainant and the witnesses present, the substance of such examination shall be reduced to writing and shall be signed by the complainant and the witnesses and also by the magistrate.

The following are the petitions and applications filed by the defence counsel

1. Petition u/s.205 Cr P C (to dispense with personal attendance of the accused)
2. Petition u/s.70(2) Cr P C – recall of warrant
3. Private Complaint u/s.200 Cr P C
4. Guilty Memo u/s.241 or 252 Cr P C
5. Petition u/s.317 Cr P C
6. Bail Application u/s.436 or 437 Cr P C
7. Anticipatory Bail Application u/s.438 Cr P C
8. Petition u/s.482 Cr P C
9. Criminal Appeal u/s.374 Cr P C
10. Criminal Revision u/s.397 Cr P C

The following are the petitions and applications can be filed by the Defence council under the new criminal law – The Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita, 2023

1. Petition u/s.228 of BNSS, 2023
2. Petition u/s.72(2) of BNSS, 2023
3. Private complaint u/s.223 of BNSS, 2023

²² Dr. K. N. Chandrasekharan Pillai, (2005), R.V. Kelkar's Criminal Procedure, Eastern Book Company, Lucknow, p26; Ghirrao V. Emperor, 34 Cri L J 1009

4. Guilty memo u/s.264 of BNSS, 2023
5. Petition u/s.355 for inquiries and trial being held in the absence of accused in certain cases.
6. Bail Application u/s.478 or 479 BNSS, 2023
7. Anticipatory Bail Application u/s.482 of BNSS, 2023
8. Petition u/s.497 of BNSS, 2023 Order for custody and disposal of property pending trial
9. Petition u/s.528 BNSS
10. Criminal Appeal u/s.415 of BNSS, 2023
11. Criminal Revision u/s.438 of BNSS, 2023

Arguments of a case

The fundamental basic principle of judicial procedure is that the evidence of one party should not be received against another party without examination of witnesses having an opportunity of testing its truthfulness by cross-examination. The art of advocacy is a vital play in a case of arguments. The communication skill which earlier discussed is an important. He should be well verse in basic procedural rules and principles governing litigation in a court. He should master the basic rules and principles of law of evidence. He should have a legal understanding of the process of initiating the litigation and carefully scrutinize the merits of the case before instituting litigation. He should evaluate the type of factors in determining what relief to seek in litigation.

Conclusion

Social justice is an integral part of our constitution and is of paramount importance. As enshrined in our preamble India is a socialistic country for which social justice is imperative. One way to promote social justice is through Clinical Legal Education. Simply put, Clinical Legal Education is a term which incorporates experiential knowledge which is focused on enabling students to understand how the law works in practice. Students can learn from variety of simulations of what happens in legal practice. Cases can be acted out in their entirety, from the taking of initial instructions to a negotiated settlements or Court

hearing of a case. Legal aid is really nothing else but equal justice in action. Legal aid is in fact the delivery system of social justice. If free legal services are not provided to such an accused, the trial itself may run the risk of being vitiated as contravening Article 21 and we have no doubt that every State Government would try to avoid such a possible eventuality.²³ The imparting clinical knowledge to the law students during their academic period is most important so the Bar council of India and the other governmental organizations shall support the clinical system of legal education in order to shape the litigant law graduates in India.

²³ Hussainara Khatoon v. State of Bihar; AIR 1979 SC 1360